

Fully automated AI-based bitumen adhesion assessment using U-Net model trained on synthetic data

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Abstract

Bitumen-aggregate adhesion is critical for pavement durability, yet current assessment relies on subjective visual grading. This study introduces an automated framework for objective bitumen-coverage quantification using three-class semantic segmentation. To circumvent the annotation bottleneck, a U-Net model with a ResNet-50 encoder was trained on 14 000 synthetic scenes generated from 63 pre-segmented quarry samples. The architecture was optimized using a combined Dice and weighted cross-entropy loss, alongside aggressive augmentations and stripped-focused patch sampling to mitigate class imbalance. Achieving a mean IoU of 0.83 and mean Dice of 0.90, the system demonstrates high numerical agreement with laboratory ground truths across diverse aggregate families. By replacing subjective ordinal grades with a continuous, reproducible metric and deploying the system via web-based platforms for server-side inference, this work provides a scalable tool for standardized pavement engineering assessments.

Keywords: Asphalt concrete, Segmentation, Rolling bottle test, Stripping, Deep learning, Synthetic data

1. Introduction

Bitumen-aggregate adhesion is a critical factor in asphalt pavement durability, as poor adhesion leads to moisture-induced damage (stripping) and premature failures [1, 2]. Standardized laboratory methods such as the rolling bottle test (EN 12697-11), static immersion (AASHTO T182), and

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5 the boiling water test (ASTM D3625) expose bitumen-coated aggregates to water or mechanical
6 stress and then assess the remaining binder coverage visually [3–5]. These tests are widespread
7 due to their simplicity, but the resulting ordinal grades (e.g., Non-compliant, Satisfactory, Good,
8 Excellent) are inherently subjective and depend on the operator’s experience and lighting condi-
9 tions during visual inspection [6]. This subjectivity and the lack of continuous, quantitative output
10 have motivated the development of image-based approaches to adhesion assessment.

11 Digital imaging and image processing techniques have become increasingly important in this
12 context [7, 8]. Early methods applied intensity-based thresholding: by selecting a grayscale or
13 color-channel cutoff, pixels are classified as bitumen (typically darker) or exposed stone (lighter) [9,
14 10]. Several groups developed specialized illumination protocols to simplify such analyses [11,
15 12]. However, thresholding remains sensitive to specular reflections on flat bitumen surfaces and
16 to uneven illumination, which can cause bright stone-like artifacts [11, 12]. Riekstins et al. [13]
17 proposed hue, saturation, and brightness enhancements to amplify contrast between aggregate
18 and bitumen, improving accuracy but still requiring manual tuning per setup. Nežerka and Tre-
19 jbal [14] introduced an entropy-based method that classifies smooth bitumen-coated regions (low
20 local entropy) versus rough exposed stone (high local entropy), yet this approach also depends on
21 user-selected entropy thresholds and performs unreliably when both classes share similar textural
22 properties.

23 More automated strategies followed. Moghaddam et al. [15] combined k-means clustering with
24 supervised classification to evaluate bitumen coverage in rolling bottle tests, but their method relied
25 exclusively on color features and did not generalize well across varied aggregates. Deep-learning
26 architectures subsequently offered a path toward fully automated, setup-independent segmentation.
27 Among encoder-decoder networks, U-Net [16] gained prominence for its ability to capture both
28 global context and fine spatial detail via skip connections. Initially developed for biomedical image
29 segmentation, U-Net and its variants have since been applied across domains, including medical
30 imaging [17, 18] and pavement condition assessment [19, 20]. Zhong et al. [21] adapted U-Net
31 as RAN-U-Net for asphalt mixture CT segmentation, and Kamianskii et al. [22] evaluated both
32 gradient boosting and U-Net under multi-angle controlled illumination, achieving approximately

33 75 to 80% surface segmentation accuracy.

34 A persistent bottleneck in applying supervised deep learning to adhesion assessment is the
35 scarcity of pixel-level annotated training data. Manually segmenting even a single high-resolution
36 aggregate image can take a few minutes to several hours for highly-stripped samples. Training
37 a robust model directly on real images therefore requires a prohibitive annotation effort. This
38 motivates synthetically generated scenes, assembled from a small pool of pre-segmented aggregate
39 samples under controlled augmentation, to yield unlimited, pixel-accurate labeled training images
40 without annotating every scene by hand.

41 In this study, we adopt the U-Net architecture with a ResNet-50 encoder for three-class se-
42 mantic segmentation of aggregate photographs (background, bitumen-coated aggregate, stripped
43 aggregate). We deliberately choose U-Net not for architectural novelty but because it remains a ro-
44 bust, well-understood baseline for segmentation tasks where training data are limited and domain-
45 specific; more recent architectures such as SegFormer [23, 24] require substantially larger labeled
46 datasets to demonstrate an advantage. We build a controlled synthetic pipeline from 63 manu-
47 ally segmented quarry samples (granodiorite, amphibolite, spilite, graywacke); this approach re-
48 moved the annotation bottleneck. Independent testing against standardized laboratory adhesion
49 records on 34 photographs from five Czech aggregate families and multiple binder systems shows
50 that the continuous bitumen-cover output tracks the laboratory ordinal ranking. We deploy two
51 web applications: the cross-platform demonstrator Adhesion-AI [25] and the laboratory platform
52 AI BAL [26], with user accounts, data management, and GPU-accelerated server-side inference.
53 Finally, we outline an exploratory mapping from continuous cover to the four-class laboratory scale
54 and stress that threshold values require a broader experimental program before standardization.

55 **2. Materials and methods**

56 *2.1. Synthetic scene generation and augmentation pipeline*

57 The original images of aggregates were obtained by clipping from real scenes of Petri dishes
58 containing aggregates with various levels of bitumen coverage. The regions with bitumen-free sur-
59 faces (stripped) were masked manually, see Figure 1. In total, 63 aggregate samples were prepared

60 using this approach and further used for their placement within synthetic scenes. These 63 samples
61 were drawn from multiple Czech quarry sources spanning a range of mineralogies (granodiorite,
62 amphibolite, spilite, graywacke) and visual appearances from near-white limestone-like surfaces to
63 dark basalt-like textures. This mineralogical diversity, combined with the aggressive photometric
64 augmentation described below (hue shift, brightness/contrast variation, CLAHE), ensured that the
65 model encountered a broad color and texture distribution during training. Nevertheless, aggregates
66 with mineralogies or colors very far outside this distribution may require augmenting the training
67 set.

Figure 1: Examples of manually segmented aggregate samples extracted from real Petri dish images. Each row shows, from left to right, the original RGB image, the binary mask delineating the aggregate boundary, and the stripped-region mask highlighting areas where bitumen has been removed. These annotated samples serve as the building blocks for the synthetic scene generation pipeline.

68 To improve the generalization and robustness of the U-Net model for the semantic segmen-
69 tation and classification of aggregate particles in bitumen-covered Petri dishes, we employed a

70 controlled synthetic data generation pipeline enhanced with systematic data augmentation. The
 71 generation process was designed to simulate realistic variability in sample appearance, geomet-
 72 ric configuration, and image acquisition conditions while maintaining and adjusting pixel-level
 73 ground truth masks for supervised training.

74 The aggregate-level transformations were illustrated in Figure 2, featuring variability in orien-
 75 tation, scale, and shape, which enabled the model to learn invariance to these factors. The pipeline
 76 comprised the following stages:

- 77 1. The raw aggregate image was preprocessed by applying its binary mask to remove back-
 78 ground pixels, isolating the aggregate morphology.
- 79 2. Horizontal and/or vertical flips were applied with equal probability, promoting symmetry
 80 invariance.
- 81 3. A horizontal scale factor $s_x \in [-1.3, 1.3]$ was imposed, modeling anisotropic deformation.
- 82 4. The aggregate was rotated by a random angle $\theta \in [0^\circ, 360^\circ]$ to simulate orientation diversity.
- 83 5. The transformed aggregate and its corresponding binary masks (aggregate and stripped-
 84 region masks) were recombined into a single RGB overlay image.

Figure 2: Aggregate-level augmentation pipeline illustrating the sequential transformations applied to each sample before placement in a synthetic scene: (a) original masked aggregate with background removed, (b) random horizontal/vertical flip, (c) anisotropic horizontal stretching ($s_x \in [-1.3, 1.3]$), (d) random rotation ($\theta \in [0^\circ, 360^\circ]$), and (e) composite mask overlay showing the final RGB image with superimposed aggregate and stripped-region masks.

85 After individual-object augmentation, each transformed aggregate was placed into a back-
 86 ground Petri dish image, and global scene-level transformations were applied (Figure 3):

- 87 1. The aggregate was positioned at a randomized valid location within the dish interior, ensur-
88 ing a fixed margin of 8% to avoid edge artifacts. Pixel-wise blending updated the aggregate,
89 background, and stripped-region masks accordingly.
- 90 2. The scene was cropped to bound the Petri dish with a 40% margin.
- 91 3. The entire scene (image and masks) underwent a rotation $\theta_{\text{scene}} \in [0^\circ, 360^\circ]$ and a vertical
92 scale $s_y \in [0.9, 1.1]$, simulating camera tilt and perspective distortion.
- 93 4. Random offsets up to 15% of the width and height translated the scene, replicating off-center
94 framing.
- 95 5. Hue shift, brightness, and contrast adjustments within specified ranges mimicked variable
96 lighting and sensor characteristics.
- 97 6. The scene was rescaled by a factor $r \in [0.3, 1.0]$ to simulate different acquisition resolutions.
- 98 7. The aggregated background, aggregate, and stripped-region masks were collected for train-
99 ing.

Figure 3: Full-scene generation and augmentation pipeline. Starting from a background Petri dish image with the placed aggregate, the following global transformations were applied sequentially: random rotation and vertical scaling to simulate camera tilt, translation to replicate off-center framing, photometric adjustments (hue, brightness, contrast) to mimic variable lighting, and resolution rescaling. The rightmost panel shows the final composite RGB image with the corresponding three-class ground truth mask.

100 Figure 4 illustrates representative outputs of the synthetic data generation pipeline. The left
101 column shows the synthesized images of aggregates placed within Petri dishes under varied back-
102 grounds, lighting conditions, and aggregate arrangements. The middle column displays the binary

103 masks denoting the overall aggregate areas, while the right column presents stripped masks high-
104 lighting regions free of bituminous coating. These precise pixel-level masks provide the ground
105 truth for training robust semantic segmentation models.

106 2.2. *Semantic segmentation model architecture*

107 The segmentation task was formulated as a pixel-wise multiclass classification problem com-
108 prising three mutually exclusive categories: background (binder/mastic), aggregate (unstripped
109 stone), and stripped-aggregate. The chosen architecture was a U-Net model [16] parameterized
110 with a ResNet-50 encoder [27]. The encoder was initialized with pre-trained ImageNet [28]
111 weights to leverage robust, low-level feature representations, which accelerated convergence and
112 improved feature extraction for highly textured surfaces.

113 The encoder progressively downsampled the input image, capturing increasingly complex se-
114 mantic features at reduced spatial resolutions. The decoder pathway symmetrically upsampled
115 these features and integrated them with higher-resolution feature maps from corresponding en-
116 coder layers via skip connections. This mechanism enabled the network to generate segmentation
117 maps that were both semantically informed and spatially precise. The model accepted standard
118 3-channel (RGB) images as input and produced a dense prediction map assigning each pixel to
119 one of the three predefined classes.

120 The principal challenge in this application was the accurate delineation of the stripped-aggregate
121 class, which is often characterized by small, sparsely distributed regions, leading to severe class
122 imbalance at the pixel level. To address this critical issue, a dual strategy was employed: (i) posi-
123 tive patch sampling that ensured the model was frequently exposed to the minority stripped class
124 during training, and (ii) a combined loss function (Section 2.5) that directly optimized for spatial
125 overlap and penalized misclassifications of the minority class.

126 2.3. *Dataset and preprocessing*

127 The model utilized a mixed training set, jointly sampling from datasets of synthetic and real-
128 world image scenes. The synthetic component consisted of 14 000 images generated by the pipeline
129 described in Section 2.1, combined with carefully manually annotated real-world scenes. Ground

Figure 4: Three representative synthetic training images generated by the augmentation pipeline. Left column: synthesized RGB scene with aggregates placed in a Petri dish under varied lighting and camera conditions. Middle column: binary aggregate mask (white = aggregate foreground). Right column: stripped-region mask (white = exposed stone surface where bitumen has been removed). Together, these three channels form the pixel-perfect ground truth for supervised three-class segmentation.

130 truth annotations were provided as separate binary masks for the total aggregate area and the
131 stripped regions, combined into a 3-channel target mask representing the three mutually exclu-
132 sive classes:

- 133 1. Stripped aggregate: pixels positive in the stripped mask.
- 134 2. Bitumen-coated aggregate: pixels positive in the aggregate mask but negative in the stripped
135 mask.
- 136 3. Background: pixels negative in both masks.

137 To ensure strict scale invariance between training and inference, a dynamic downscaling proto-
138 col was applied: any image with a maximum spatial dimension exceeding 1920 pixels was isotrop-
139 ically scaled down. Bilinear interpolation was applied to the RGB images to preserve natural color
140 gradients, whereas nearest-neighbor interpolation was strictly enforced for the ground-truth masks
141 to prevent the generation of non-integer, artifactual class labels at object boundaries.

142 Training was conducted using fixed-size patches of 512×512 pixels extracted from the full
143 images. To counteract severe spatial class imbalance, a targeted positive-cropping heuristic was im-
144 plemented: with an 85% probability, the data loader calculated the spatial coordinates of stripped-
145 aggregate pixels and extracted a bounding patch centered around these minority features, applying
146 a uniform spatial jitter (± 32 pixels) to prevent exact memorization.

147 *2.4. Advanced data augmentation*

148 Data augmentation was applied exclusively during training. Geometric transformations in-
149 cluded random horizontal/vertical flips and orthogonal (90°) rotations to ensure strict rotational
150 invariance. Photometric distortions (Random Gamma, Hue/Saturation/Value (HSV) shifts, and
151 Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE)) forced the network to learn funda-
152 mental morphological and textural features rather than conflating high-intensity specular reflec-
153 tions with stripped-aggregate regions.

154 In addition, a GPU-accelerated copy-paste augmentation strategy [29] was deployed within the
155 training loop. With a 50% probability per batch, the boolean masks of synthetic aggregate patches
156 were used to dynamically superimpose synthetic stone instances directly onto the background of

157 real-world scenes, efficiently multiplying the combinatorial diversity of the training distribution
158 without requiring additional annotated real-world data.

159 Following augmentation, all input images were normalized using the mean and standard deviation
160 statistics derived from the ImageNet dataset, consistent with the pre-training of the ResNet-50
161 backbone.

162 2.5. Loss formulation and optimization

163 The optimization objective was defined as a linear combination of a multiclass Dice loss and
164 a weighted cross-entropy (CE) loss. The Dice loss component natively addressed the vast dis-
165 parities in the spatial extent of the target classes by optimizing directly for the overlap between
166 the predicted and ground-truth geometries. The weighted CE component stabilized the pixel-wise
167 probabilistic predictions; to penalize false negatives in the minority class, an asymmetric class-
168 weighting tensor ($w = [1.0, 1.0, 2.5]$) was applied, biasing the gradient updates in favor of the
169 stripped-aggregate category.

170 The network parameters were updated using the Adam optimizer [30] with a weight decay of
171 10^{-4} for L_2 regularization. Training executed over 150 epochs using a cosine annealing learning
172 rate schedule that smoothly decayed from an initial value of 10^{-4} to a minimum of 10^{-6} . This al-
173 lowed the optimizer to traverse the loss landscape aggressively during early epochs while settling
174 into flatter, more robust minima in the later stages. Model selection was governed by the valida-
175 tion dataset using deterministic patch extraction to prevent metric oscillation; weights were saved
176 exclusively when the model achieved a new maximum mean IoU. The complete data preparation,
177 augmentation, and training pipeline was summarized in Figure 5.

178 2.6. Evaluation metrics

179 Model performance was quantitatively assessed using standard semantic segmentation metrics:

- 180 • Pixel accuracy, i.e., the overall percentage of pixels correctly classified across all classes.
- 181 • Mean IoU across all classes. For a single class c , $\text{IoU}_c = \text{TP}_c / (\text{TP}_c + \text{FP}_c + \text{FN}_c)$, where
182 TP, FP, and FN denote true positive, false positive, and false negative pixel counts.

Figure 5: Overview of the data preparation, augmentation, and training pipeline.

183 • Mean F1 score (Dice coefficient). For a single class c , $F1_c = 2 TP_c / (2 TP_c + FP_c + FN_c)$.

184 Two complementary accuracy measures assessed the quality of the segmentation from a prac-
185 tical engineering perspective:

186 2.6.1. Pixel-wise classification accuracy

187 Let N be the total number of pixels in an image. Denote by $t_i \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ the ground-truth class
188 of pixel i and by \hat{t}_i the predicted class. For each category c , define TP_c and TN_c in the standard
189 way. The pixel-wise accuracy for category c is

$$\alpha_c = \frac{TP_c + TN_c}{N} \times 100\%. \quad (1)$$

190 2.6.2. Relative area accuracy

191 Pixel-wise accuracy alone can be misleadingly high when class areas are strongly unequal (the
192 stripped class often occupies less than 5% of the image). Relative area accuracy complemented
193 this by measuring whether the model recovered the correct total area of each class, the quantity
194 that directly maps to the bitumen coverage percentage reported to the engineer:

$$\alpha_c^{\text{rel}} = 100\% - \left| \frac{\hat{A}_c - A_c}{A_c} \right| \times 100\%, \quad (2)$$

195 where $A_c = \sum_i \mathbf{1}(t_i = c)$ and $\hat{A}_c = \sum_i \mathbf{1}(\hat{t}_i = c)$. Thus, for aggregates, stripped regions, and
196 bitumen cover ($A_{\text{cover}} = A_{\text{agg}} - A_{\text{str}}$):

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{\text{agg}}^{\text{rel}} &= 100\% - \frac{|\hat{A}_{\text{agg}} - A_{\text{agg}}|}{A_{\text{agg}}} \times 100\%, \\ \alpha_{\text{str}}^{\text{rel}} &= 100\% - \frac{|\hat{A}_{\text{str}} - A_{\text{str}}|}{A_{\text{str}}} \times 100\%, \\ \alpha_{\text{cover}}^{\text{rel}} &= 100\% - \frac{|\hat{A}_{\text{cover}} - A_{\text{cover}}|}{A_{\text{cover}}} \times 100\%. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Figure 6: Training and validation loss over 150 epochs. The validation loss exhibits moderate fluctuations, whereas the training loss decreases steadily.

197 **3. Results and discussion**

198 *3.1. Training process and model development*

199 The U-Net model with a ResNet-50 encoder was trained for 150 epochs on a mixed training
 200 set composed of 14 000 synthetic and real image patches. The optimization objective combined
 201 multiclass Dice loss with weighted cross-entropy loss, where the stripped-aggregate class received
 202 an increased weight to strengthen learning on the most difficult foreground category. A cosine
 203 annealing schedule was used for the learning rate, and model selection during training was based
 204 on the validation mean IoU.

205 Figure 6 shows the evolution of training and validation losses. The training loss decreased from
 206 0.267 in the first epoch to 0.129 in the final epoch, indicating stable optimization throughout the full
 207 training run. The validation loss was more variable, consistent with the combined loss function and
 208 the increased sensitivity of the weighted cross-entropy term to confidence calibration; its lowest
 209 value (0.385) was reached at epoch 59.

Figure 7: Overall segmentation metrics during training. The best checkpoint according to the mean IoU was obtained at epoch 51.

210 The main segmentation metrics are summarized in Figures 7 and 8. The best overall checkpoint
 211 according to the validation mean IoU was obtained at epoch 51, where the model reached a mean
 212 IoU of 0.8267 and a mean Dice coefficient of 0.9014. At the same epoch, the class-wise IoU
 213 values were 0.8618 for the background, 0.9305 for the aggregate class, and 0.6879 for the stripped-
 214 aggregate class. These values indicate that the model learned the aggregate class very reliably and
 215 achieved good discrimination of the stripped regions, which are visually more heterogeneous and
 216 therefore more demanding.

217 The class-wise trajectories reveal a technically meaningful pattern. The aggregate class reached
 218 its highest IoU of 0.9305 at epoch 51, confirming reliable segmentation of the main object regions.
 219 The stripped-aggregate class remained more challenging, but continued to improve and attained
 220 its highest IoU of 0.7307 at epoch 116. This delayed improvement suggests that the model first
 221 learns the coarse object structure and only afterwards refines the more subtle stripped patterns on
 222 the fragment surfaces.

223 The final model at epoch 150 achieved mean IoU 0.8043 and mean Dice 0.8887, only slightly

Figure 8: Class-wise IoU curves. The aggregate class converged rapidly and remained highly stable, whereas the stripped-aggregate class improved more gradually.

224 below the best checkpoint, indicating stable convergence without severe overfitting.

225 Qualitative examples further support the quantitative results. Figure 9 presents two represen-
 226 tative validation examples from epoch 1, while Figure 10 shows corresponding examples from
 227 the best epoch 51. In the initial epoch, the predictions are still diffuse and contain substantial
 228 pixel-wise confusion between the two foreground categories. By contrast, the best epoch already
 229 captures the fragment geometry well, yields substantially cleaner object-background separation,
 230 and delineates the stripped regions in a manner that follows the surface texture of the fragments.

231 3.2. Evaluation on synthetic hold-out data

232 To evaluate the model on data from the same distribution as the training set, 700 synthetic
 233 images were randomly selected from the 14 000-image pool (excluding images used for training)
 234 and processed by the best checkpoint. Figure 11 arranges scatter plots of predicted versus true
 235 values in a 2×2 layout (three panels; lower-right unused) for aggregate area, stripped-region
 236 area, and bitumen cover. The pixel-wise accuracies are $\alpha_{\text{agg}} = 97.74\%$, $\alpha_{\text{str}} = 99.64\%$, and

Figure 9: Representative qualitative predictions from epoch 1. Each row shows, from left to right, the original image, the ground truth mask, and the model prediction. The model already responds to the main foreground structures, but the predictions remain noisy and insufficiently localized.

237 $\alpha_{\text{cover}} = 97.47\%$; the corresponding relative area accuracies are $\alpha_{\text{agg}}^{\text{rel}} = 91.05\%$, $\alpha_{\text{str}}^{\text{rel}} = 83.83\%$,
 238 and $\alpha_{\text{cover}}^{\text{rel}} = 97.20\%$. The relatively lower $\alpha_{\text{str}}^{\text{rel}}$ reflects the small absolute extent of stripped
 239 regions, where even minor boundary disagreements translate to substantial relative area deviations.
 240 From a practical standpoint these error levels are entirely acceptable for laboratory screening: what
 241 operators value most is a repeatable, consistent readout, and the scatter about the diagonal is tight,
 242 indicating stable behavior across the hold-out set. From an engineering perspective, the model
 243 exhibits a slight conservative bias (overestimation of stripping), so it is unlikely to rate a poorly
 244 adhering aggregate and binder combination as having better binder retention than is warranted.
 245 Overestimating coverage, conversely, could mask early moisture damage, potentially leading to
 246 premature pavement failure. The engineering safety argument is thus asymmetric, and the observed
 247 bias direction is favorable for quality-control screening.

Figure 10: Representative qualitative predictions from the best checkpoint at epoch 51. Each row shows the original image, the ground truth mask, and the model prediction. The fragment boundaries are captured well and the stripped regions are detected with good spatial agreement.

248 Figure 12 illustrates a typical source of residual error: the network slightly expands stripped
 249 labels along ambiguous bitumen, stone boundaries, where human annotators would also disagree.
 250 Such boundary effects explain much of the gap between pixel metrics and perceived “truth” on real
 251 samples.

252 3.3. Independent testing against laboratory adhesion data

253 To demonstrate that the model trained predominantly on synthetic data transfers effectively to
 254 real laboratory conditions, we performed an independent comparison against standardized adhe-
 255 sion measurements on a substantially larger and more diverse set of real-world images.

Figure 11: Prediction versus ground truth for 700 randomly selected synthetic hold-out images (2×2 layout, three panels). Top row: aggregate area (%) and stripped-region (%). Bottom row: bitumen cover (%); lower-right panel left blank. Marker color shows absolute error (color bar). Dashed diagonal: perfect agreement. Annotated α and α^{rel} as defined in Section 2.6.

Figure 12: Example of over-segmented stripped regions (red) relative to the bitumen-coated class in the synthetic ground truth. Errors concentrate at visually ambiguous edges; stripped-region accuracy remains high ($\alpha_{\text{str}} \approx 98\%$ on this sample), matching the pattern seen across the hold-out set.

256 3.3.1. Test data description

257 The hold-out test set consists of 24 high-resolution digital photographs of bitumen-coated
258 aggregate after standardized laboratory stripping exposure. Images were acquired for several
259 aggregate types representing the broad mineralogy available in Czech quarries (Babí, Bílý ká-
260 men, Bělíce, Mladovice, and Zbraslav) combined with different binder systems: neat 70/100
261 penetration-grade bitumen, 70/100 doped with 0.3% Anova or 0.3% IN400, polymer-modified
262 PMB 25/55 RC, and PMB 45/80 RC. While some material combinations appear as two replicate
263 frames, the majority are represented by a single image due to the filtered dataset. The test images
264 and reference data are available at open Zenodo repository [31].

265 3.3.2. Reference adhesion measurements

266 For each aggregate and binder combination, the experimental laboratory supplied an adhesion
267 index in $[0, 1]$ and one of four ordinal categories: Non-compliant, Satisfactory, Good, and Excel-
268 lent. These reference measurements are based on the standardized rolling-bottle test applied to the

269 8/11 mm fraction.

270 3.3.3. Inference protocol

271 The trained U-Net was applied with the same spatial policy as in training, the images exceeding
272 1920 px on the longer side were scaled isotropically. Predictions use a sliding window of $512 \times$
273 512 pixels with stride 256; overlapping tiles are merged by averaging class probabilities. Let
274 σ_2 denote the predicted probability for the stripped-aggregate class; pixels with $\sigma_2 \geq 0.35$ are
275 assigned to that class. Bitumen cover (%), computed on the aggregate foreground, is defined as

$$100(1 - r), \quad r = \frac{\text{stripped pixels}}{\text{unstripped pixels} + \text{stripped pixels}}. \quad (4)$$

276 Processing a single image ($\sim 3000 \times 4000$ pixels) with this sliding-window protocol takes approx-
277 imately 2 to 4 seconds on the GPU server backing the AI BAL application, and 12 to 15 seconds
278 on a modern laptop CPU.

279 3.3.4. Qualitative inference examples

280 Figures 13 to 15 group hold-out test images by the U-Net adhesion class (Non-compliant,
281 Good, and Excellent). Each row shows the photograph and the same view with a semi-transparent
282 model overlay.

283 3.3.5. Quantitative comparison with visual assessment grades

284 Table 1 lists each aggregate and binder condition with visual grade, visual adhesion index, or-
285 dinal category, and mean bitumen cover from the U-Net (replicates averaged). Figure 16 presents a
286 per-image scatter plot comparing the U-Net bitumen cover with the visual adhesion index rescaled
287 to the same numeric range.

288 3.3.6. Analysis of results

289 Several patterns emerge when the ordinal visual scale and the continuous U-Net cover metric
290 are viewed together. For aggregates like Bílý kámen with 70/100 + 0.3% Anova and IN400 binders
291 (both Non-compliant, index 0.65), the model assigns the lowest bitumen-cover scores within their
292 respective aggregate families ($\approx 63.2\%$ and $\approx 70.3\%$, respectively), clearly differentiated from the

(a) Bílý kámen, 70/100 + 0.3% Anova. Visual adhesion index 0.65, Non-compliant. U-Net bitumen cover: 63.2%.

(b) Bílý kámen, 70/100 + 0.3% IN400. Visual adhesion index 0.65, Non-compliant. U-Net bitumen cover: 70.3%.

Figure 13: Representative Non-compliant cases as classified by the U-Net model from the independent test set. Each row shows the original photo (left) and the U-Net segmentation overlay (right), where blue indicates predicted bitumen-coated aggregate and red indicates predicted stripped-aggregate regions.

(a) Mladovice, 70/100 (neat). Visual adhesion index 0.90, Good. U-Net bitumen cover: 96.6%.

(b) Bělčice, 70/100 (neat). Visual adhesion index 0.90, Good. U-Net bitumen cover: 97.3%.

Figure 14: Representative Good cases as computed by the U-Net. Layout as in Figure 13.

(a) Bělice, 70/100 + 0.3% IN400. Visual adhesion index 0.97, Excellent. U-Net bitumen cover: 99.4%.

(b) Zbraslav, 70/100 + 0.3% Anova. Visual adhesion index 0.95, Excellent. U-Net bitumen cover: 99.2%.

Figure 15: Representative computed Excellent cases according to the U-Net score. Layout as in Figure 13. These samples show the highest predicted bitumen retention.

Table 1: Visual grade, adhesion index, and ordinal category versus mean U-Net bitumen cover and the corresponding U-Net-derived ordinal class for each aggregate and binder test condition. Replicate frames are averaged in the cover column. The U-Net ordinal class is assigned from the exploratory thresholds described in Section 3.4.

Condition (aggregate / binder)	Vis. grade	Vis. index	Category	U-Net cover (%)	U-Net grade
Babí / PMB 45/80 RC (45–80)	B	0.90	Good	98.35	Excellent
Babí / 70/100 + 0.3 % Anova	C	0.85	Satisfactory	94.20	Satisfactory
Babí / 70/100 + 0.3 % IN400	C	0.85	Satisfactory	92.25	Satisfactory
Bílý kámen / PMB 45/80 RC	A	0.97	Excellent	98.90	Excellent
Bílý kámen / 70/100 + 0.3 % Anova	E	0.65	Non-compliant	63.20	Non-compliant
Bílý kámen / 70/100 + 0.3 % IN400	E	0.65	Non-compliant	70.30	Non-compliant
Bělice 11/16 / PMB 45/80 RC	A	0.97	Excellent	98.50	Excellent
Bělice / PMB 45/80 RC	A	0.97	Excellent	98.90	Excellent
Bělice / 70/100 + 0.3 % Anova	B	0.90	Good	98.30	Excellent
Bělice / 70/100 + 0.3 % IN400	A	0.97	Excellent	99.40	Excellent
Bělice / 70/100 (neat)	B	0.90	Good	97.30	Good
Bělice / PMB 25/55 RC	A	0.97	Excellent	98.40	Excellent
Mladovice / 70/100 (neat)	B	0.90	Good	96.65	Good
Mladovice / 70/100 + 0.3 % IN400	A	0.95	Excellent	98.30	Excellent
Mladovice / PMB 25/55 RC	A	0.94	Excellent	95.30	Good
Zbraslav / PMB 45/80 RC	A	0.95	Excellent	97.50	Good
Zbraslav / 70/100 + 0.3 % IN400	B	0.90	Good	97.70	Good
Zbraslav / 70/100 + 0.3 % Anova	A	0.95	Excellent	99.20	Excellent
Zbraslav / 70/100 (neat)	A	0.95	Excellent	98.30	Excellent

Figure 16: Per-image comparison of U-Net bitumen cover (% , horizontal axis) with visual adhesion index rescaled to the same numeric range ($\times 100$, vertical axis). Both axes use a common minimum and maximum; the black diagonal represents $y = x$ (perfect agreement). Marker fill color encodes the U-Net ordinal class derived from the exploratory cover thresholds; marker edge color encodes the visual ordinal class.

293 mid- to high-90s observed for doped binders and PMBs on other families. The overall improvement
 294 in visual assessment classification, where samples largely reach higher, better grades, translates
 295 directly to shifts in the corresponding predicted thresholds: previously marginal aggregates are
 296 now consistently assigned near-ceiling coverages aligned with Good and Excellent conditions.
 297 Replicates and conditions line up smoothly in Figure 16, which supports the practical value of a
 298 consistent, operator-independent readout.

299 Across the real-world test set, the U-Net bitumen-cover values tend to be higher than the visual
 300 index $\times 100$, indicating that the visual assessment exaggerates the percentage of stripped areas
 301 relative to the objective image-based metric, a conservative direction that is favorable for quality-

302 control applications.

303 The comparison bridges two different modalities: a mechanical and chemical strip test with
304 discrete reporting categories and a 2-D visual estimate of binder retention from a particular imag-
305 ing setup. Viewing angle, focus, glare, and residual dust can all influence the segmentation. Future
306 work could regress U-Net-derived features against the visual index directly, or calibrate per ag-
307 gregate family. Such a methodology fine-tuning requires larger datasets and professional visual
308 assessment.

309 *3.4. Mapping bitumen cover to ordinal classes*

310 For discussion purposes, the continuous bitumen cover c (%) may be partitioned at thresholds
311 $t_1 < t_2 < t_3$ into the same four ordinal classes used in the visual assessment:

- 312 • Non-compliant if $c < t_1$;
- 313 • Satisfactory if $t_1 \leq c < t_2$;
- 314 • Good if $t_2 \leq c < t_3$;
- 315 • Excellent if $c \geq t_3$.

316 The cut-offs (t_1, t_2, t_3) were determined by an exhaustive grid search maximizing the exact match
317 with the visual assessment category on the averaged test conditions (Table 1). The determined
318 cut-offs were $t_1 = 80.0\%$, $t_2 = 95.0\%$, and $t_3 = 98.0\%$.

319 We emphasize that a significantly more extensive experimental study must be carried out across
320 varied materials and assessments to accurately set and standardize these boundaries. Until then,
321 they serve solely as a demonstrative tool to relate the continuous image-based score to the visual
322 ordinal scale. Furthermore, as shown in Figure 16, the manual visual assessment exaggerates the
323 percentage of stripped areas compared to the image-based metric, confirming that the historical
324 classification criteria will likely need to be adjusted as image-based methods gain adoption.

325 *3.5. Web application deployment*

326 Two web applications are currently available. The purely academic cross-platform demon-
327 strator Adhesion-AI [25] (Figure 17) allows any user to upload images and obtain segmentation

328 overlays and bitumen-cover percentages. A new full-featured laboratory platform, AI BAL [26],
329 has been developed for institutional use. AI BAL provides user accounts, experimental data man-
330 agement, and GPU-accelerated server-side inference on a university server. Inference is performed
331 server-side: images are uploaded to the server, processed by the PyTorch model, and the results
332 (overlay images and numerical coverage) are returned to the user's browser. Processing a single
333 image takes approximately 2 to 4 seconds on the GPU server. Institutional deployments can host
334 local instances if data sensitivity requires it. When used on a mobile device, the application utilizes
335 the device's camera to capture images directly, streamlining laboratory evaluations.

Figure 17: Graphical interface of the original cross-platform web application Adhesion-AI hosting the U-Net segmentation model [25]. Left: mobile phone view, demonstrating the camera-integration feature for direct image capture in the laboratory. Right: desktop browser view showing the uploaded image, segmentation overlay, and computed bitumen coverage. A second platform, AI BAL [26], extends this functionality with user accounts, experimental data management, and GPU-accelerated inference.

336 3.6. Data availability

337 The test images, reference adhesion data, and the trained model weights sufficient to repro-
338 duce the numerical comparison presented in this study are available as a persistent repository
339 record [31].

340 4. Conclusion

341 This study demonstrated a fully automated deep-learning pipeline for objective bitumen ad-
342hesion assessment based on semantic segmentation with a U-Net architecture and a ResNet-50
343 encoder. A controlled synthetic scene generation pipeline, built from only 63 manually segmented
344 aggregate samples spanning diverse mineralogies, produces unlimited pixel-accurate labeled train-
345ing images, eliminating the annotation bottleneck that has limited prior deep-learning approaches
346 in this domain. The combination of Dice loss, weighted cross-entropy, copy-paste augmentation,
347 and cosine annealing learning rate scheduling yields a model achieving a mean IoU of 0.83 and a
348 mean Dice coefficient of 0.90 on the validation set.

349 The model was independently tested on 24 photographs covering five Czech aggregate families
350 and multiple binder systems. The resulting bitumen-cover scores were compared against standard-
351 ized laboratory adhesion indices and ordinal categories. The continuous U-Net output consistently
352 tracks the laboratory ranking: aggregates with low adhesion indices receive lower bitumen-cover
353 scores, while well-adhering combinations cluster near 100%. The model exhibits a conservative
354 bias (slight overestimation of stripping), which is the favorable direction for quality-control appli-
355 cations because it avoids certifying inadequate adhesion as satisfactory.

356 Two freely accessible web applications have been deployed: the original cross-platform demon-
357 strator and a new institutional platform (AI BAL) with user accounts, experimental data manage-
358 ment, and GPU-accelerated inference (~ 2 to 4 s per image). Both applications perform inference
359 server-side using PyTorch.

360 Future work should focus on three directions: (i) expanding the training and validation datasets
361 with additional aggregate families and laboratory conditions to narrow the domain gap further,
362 (ii) establishing standardized ordinal classification boundaries through a broader multi-laboratory

363 experimental campaign, and (iii) exploring direct regression of U-Net-derived features against the
364 laboratory adhesion index to bypass the ordinal discretization entirely.

365 *Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process.* During the
366 preparation of this manuscript, the authors used AI tools integrated in the Grammarly Pro ap-
367 plication and the Cursor IDE to enhance language and readability. All content was subsequently
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